

Reactivity ratios determination and NMR characterization of 2-hydroxy ethyl methacrylate and methyl methacrylate copolymers

Sunita Hooda^{a*} and Ashok Kumar Goyal^b

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Acharya Narendra Dev College, Govindpuri, Kalkaji, New Delhi-110 019, India
E-mail : sunitahooda@hotmail.com

^bDepartment of Chemistry, Indian Institute of Technology Delhi, Hauz Khas, New Delhi-110 016, India
E-mail : goyalak_chem@rediffmail.com

Manuscript received 26 November 2007, revised 13 May 2008, accepted 28 May 2008

Abstract : NMR has proven to be one of the most informative technique for the investigation of copolymer microstructure as chemical shifts are sensitive to compositional and configurational sequences of copolymers. The HEMA/MMA copolymers were prepared by free radical bulk polymerization at 70 °C. The copolymer composition was determined from ¹H NMR spectrum which is then used to determine the reactivity ratios. The reactivity ratios obtained from KT, EVM and least square methods are $r_{\text{HEMA}} = 0.98$, $r_{\text{MMA}} = 0.82$; $r_{\text{HEMA}} = 0.88$, $r_{\text{MMA}} = 0.81$ and $r_{\text{HEMA}} = 0.92$, $r_{\text{MMA}} = 0.81$ respectively. ¹H and ¹³C{¹H} NMR spectra were analyzed with the help of DEPT, 2D HSQC and 2D TOCSY spectrum. The long range interactions of carbonyl carbon with methoxy protons and oxy methylene carbon with hydroxyl proton were determined with the help of heteronuclear multiple bond coherence (HMBC) spectrum. With the help of 2D spectra it was found that carbonyl, α -methyl and quaternary carbon of HEMA and MMA unit were sensitive to various configurational sequences as in poly(2-hydroxy ethyl methacrylate) and poly(methyl methacrylate). The carbonyl and oxymethylene carbons showed long range interactions with methoxy and hydroxyl protons respectively.

Keywords : Reactivity ratios, NMR, 2-hydroxy ethyl methacrylate, methyl methacrylate, microstructure, polymerization.

Introduction

2-Hydroxy ethyl methacrylate is a commercially important monomer that is widely used in the manufacture of soft contact lenses and intraocular lenses^{1,2}. HEMA copolymers have found numerous medical applications due to their acceptable biocompatibility^{3,4}. Amongst other applications these copolymers have been identified as having potential use in controlled drug delivery systems^{5,6}. NMR spectroscopy has provided valuable information on sequence distribution and stereo regularity of copolymers^{7,8}. High resolution NMR spectroscopy is a powerful tool for nondestructive structural investigation of matter^{9,10}. The copolymerization of 2-hydroxy ethyl methacrylate with other acrylates have been reported earlier also^{11,12}. Various coworkers have reported the NMR study of methyl methacrylate with other vinyl monomers^{13,14}. Ydens *et al.*¹⁵ have reported the copolymerization of 2-HEMA-methyl methacrylate through atom transfer radical polymerization (ATRP) but to the best of our knowledge, no work has been reported on microstructure of 2-

HEMA and methyl methacrylate copolymers. In this work, HEMA/MMA copolymers of different compositions were prepared by free radical bulk polymerization. One- and two-dimensional NMR spectra were used to study microstructure of HEMA/MMA copolymers. The carbonyl, methyl, methylene and quaternary carbons were found to be sensitive toward configurational sequences but insensitive to compositional sequences. 2D-TOCSY spectrum was used to explain ¹H-¹H correlation in HEMA/MMA copolymers while 2D HMBC spectrum was used to determine long range interactions between different groups.

Experimental

2-Hydroxy ethyl methacrylate (HEMA) and methyl methacrylate (MMA) monomers were vacuum distilled and stored below 5 °C. A series of HEMA/MMA copolymers of different composition were prepared by free radical bulk polymerization using azo bis isobutronitrile as an initiator at 70 °C under nitrogen atmosphere. The percent conversion was kept below 10% by precipitating the copolymers in hexane. The copolymers were further

purified by precipitation method using methanol as a solvent for higher composition of HEMA unit and chloroform as a solvent for lower composition of HEMA unit. The various types of NMR spectra were recorded¹⁶ by dissolving the copolymers in DMSO-*d*₆ at 80 °C.

Results and discussion

Reactivity ratios determination :

The composition of HEMA/MMA copolymers was determined from ¹H NMR spectrum (Fig. 1). The intensity of -OH proton of HEMA unit and combined intensity

and in copolymers. The copolymer composition data were used to determine reactivity ratios of co monomers using Kelen-Tudos (KT)¹⁷ method. The reactivity ratios from error in variable method (EVM)¹⁸ were calculated using the reactivity ratios obtained from KT method along with copolymer composition data. The reactivity ratios of co monomers in HEMA/MMA copolymers obtained from KT, EVM and least square methods¹⁹ are $r_{\text{HEMA}} = 0.98$, $r_{\text{MMA}} = 0.82$; $r_{\text{HEMA}} = 0.88$, $r_{\text{MMA}} = 0.81$ and $r_{\text{HEMA}} = 0.92$, $r_{\text{MMA}} = 0.81$ respectively. The values are to-

Fig. 1. ¹H NMR spectrum of HEMA/MMA copolymer ($F_{\text{HEMA}} = 0.54$) in DMSO-*d*₆.

of α -CH₃ protons of HEMA and MMA unit were used to determine copolymer composition using the following relation :

$$F_{\text{HEMA}} = \frac{I(-\text{OH})_{\text{HEMA}}}{I(-\text{OCH}_3)_{\text{HEMA+HEMA}} / 3}$$

Table 1 shows the co monomer mole fractions in feed

Table 1. Copolymer composition data for HEMA/MMA copolymers

Sr. No.	f_{HEMA}	F_{HEMA}
1.	0.10	0.13
2.	0.20	0.20
3.	0.40	0.38
4.	0.50	0.54
5.	0.70	0.74

f_{HEMA} = in feed composition of HEMA unit.

F_{HEMA} = composition of HEMA unit in copolymer.

tally different from the reported values²⁰, which may be due to a different method of polymerization i.e. solution polymerization using benzoyl peroxide as an initiator.

¹³C{¹H} and 2D HSQC studies :

The completely assigned ¹³C{¹H} NMR spectrum of HEMA/MMA copolymer ($F_{\text{H}} = 0.54$) in DMSO-*d*₆ at 80 °C is shown in Fig. 2. The overlapped resonance signals around δ 50.0–55.0 ppm can be resolved by DEPT-135 NMR spectrum (Fig. 3). In DEPT-135 NMR spectrum methylene carbon resonances appeared as negative phase while methine and methyl carbon resonances appeared as a positive phase. So the positive resonance signal around δ 51.40 ppm was assigned to methyl carbon resonance of MMA unit. The inverted resonance signals around δ 50.25 and δ 53.50 ppm were assigned to methylene carbon resonances of MMA and HEMA unit in the copolymers respectively.

Fig. 2. $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ spectrum of HEMA/MMA copolymer ($F_{\text{HEMA}} = 0.54$) in $\text{DMSO-}d_6$, (a) expanded α -methyl, (b) expanded quaternary carbon resonance signal.

The expanded α -methyl carbon resonance signal of HEMA/MMA copolymer is shown in Fig. 2a. The resonance signals at δ 20.81, 18.55 and 16.20 ppm are assigned to mm, mr and rr triads configurational sequences respectively as in homo polymer i.e. PHEMA²¹ and PMMA¹⁶. The 2D HSQC spectrum (Fig. 5a) of α -methyl region also shows the same pattern as in PHEMA and PMMA. The cross peaks 1, 2 and 3 are assigned to mm, mr and rr triads configurational sequences which also confirms that α -methyl carbon is sensitive towards configurational sequences only.

The expanded quaternary carbon resonance signal of HEMA and MMA unit in HEMA/MMA copolymer is shown in Fig. 2b. In HEMA/MMA copolymer, the resonance signals at δ 45.26, 44.68 and 44.21 ppm are assigned to mm, mr and rr triads configurational sequences. The splitting pattern in HEMA/MMA copolymer is almost of the same type as in PMMA¹⁶ and PHEMA²¹, which indicates the insensitivity of quaternary carbon resonance signals of HEMA and MMA unit in HEMA/MMA copolymers towards compositional sequences.

The expanded overlapped carbonyl carbon resonance

Fig. 3. DEPT-135 spectrum of HEMA/MMA copolymer ($F_{\text{HEMA}} = 0.54$) in $\text{DMSO-}d_6$.

signals of HEMA and MMA units in HEMA/MMA copolymers of different compositions are shown in Fig. 4. In HEMA/MMA copolymer, the resonance signals 4, 5 and 6 are assigned to rr, mr and mm triads configurational sequences. The splitting pattern in HEMA/MMA copolymer is almost of the same type as that in PHEMA and PMMA indicates that carbonyl carbon resonance signal of HEMA and MMA unit in HEMA/MMA copolymers is not sensitive to compositional sequences. The intensity of mr resonance signal is more than rr in copolymers having higher HEMA content and in PHEMA but in PMMA intensity of rr triad is more than that of mr triad which is due to the interaction of carbonyl carbon with -OH group in PHEMA. Since the intensity variation of mr and rr triad in PMMA and PHEMA is reverse of each other so there is no regular trend in the variation of intensity of mr and rr triads in copolymer. Similar trend is also observed in the variation of quaternary, α -methylene and β -methylene carbon resonance signals.

The methylene carbon resonance region of HEMA/MMA copolymer also shows almost similar splitting pattern as that in homo polymers i.e. PHEMA and PMMA indicates its sensitivity towards tacticity and not towards

compositional sequences. The cross peak regions 7, 8 and 9 in 2D HSQC spectrum (Fig. 5b) are assigned to mmm + mrr, mnr and rnr + rrr tetrad configurational sequences respectively. The 2D HSQC spectrum shows its insensitivity towards compositional sequences. The cross peak 10 (Fig. 5b), is assigned to the coupling of -OCH₃ carbon of MMA unit with protons. Similarly, the cross peaks 11 and 12 are assigned to coupling of -CH₂O and -OCH₂ carbons of HEMA unit with protons respectively.

2D TOCSY studies :

In order to understand the connectivity and confirm the various couplings in the copolymer chain, the TOCSY spectrum was recorded. The three bond coupling between the protons of directly coupled protons in HEMA/MMA copolymer can be seen clearly in TOCSY spectrum in short mixing time (4 ms). The cross peak at δ 1.45/1.75 ppm (13) is due to the coupling between methylene protons of HEMA and MMA unit (Fig. 6a). The various geminal coupling between the protons of -CH₂ (HEMA) and -CH₂ (MMA) are also possible which are difficult to distinguish due to the low value of coupling constants. The cross peak at δ 3.60/4.75 ppm (14) is assigned to the

Fig. 4. The expanded overlapped carbonyl carbon resonance signal of HEMA and MMA unit in HEMA/MMA copolymer of different composition : (a) PHEMA, (b) $F_{\text{HEMA}} = 0.74$, (c) $F_{\text{HEMA}} = 0.54$, (d) $F_{\text{HEMA}} = 0.20$, (e) PMMA in $\text{DMSO-}d_6$.

Fig. 5. The expanded 2D HSQC spectrum of HEMA/MMA copolymer ($F_{\text{HEMA}} = 0.54$) : (a) α -methyl region, (b) methylene region and oxy methylene region in $\text{DMSO-}d_6$.

Fig. 6. The 2D TOCSY spectrum of HEMA/MMA copolymer ($F_{\text{HEMA}} = 0.54$) showing coupling in (a) methylene region, (b) oxy methylene region in $\text{DMSO-}d_6$.

Fig. 7. The 2D HMBC spectrum of HEMA/MMA copolymer ($F_{\text{HEMA}} = 0.54$) showing coupling in (a) carbonyl region, (b) oxy methylene region in $\text{DMSO-}d_6$.

coupling of $-\text{CH}_2\text{O}-$ protons with hydroxyl proton of HEMA unit while the cross peaks at δ 3.55/3.95 ppm (15) is due to the coupling of $-\text{CH}_2\text{O}-$ protons with $-\text{OCH}_2$ protons of HEMA unit (Fig. 6b).

2D HMBC studies :

The 2D heteronuclear multiple bond correlation

(HMBC) experiment has become a powerful technique for the detection of heteronuclear long range couplings. The HMBC spectrum of HEMA/MMA copolymer ($F_{\text{HEMA}} = 0.54$) is shown in Fig. 7. The carbonyl carbon of HEMA and MMA unit shows long range interaction with methoxy protons (Fig. 7a). The cross peaks 16, 17 and 18 have been assigned to the coupling of carbonyl

carbon centered in mm, mr and rr triad configurational sequences with methoxy protons (-OCH₃) of MMA unit. The -CH₂O carbon and -OCH₂O carbon shows interaction with hydroxyl protons that have been assigned to cross peaks 19 and 20 respectively (Fig. 7b).

Conclusions :

The reactivity ratios of co monomers in HEMA/MMA copolymers are $r_{\text{HEMA}} = 0.98$, $r_{\text{MMA}} = 0.82$; $r_{\text{HEMA}} = 0.88$, $r_{\text{MMA}} = 0.81$ and $r_{\text{HEMA}} = 0.92$, $r_{\text{MMA}} = 0.81$ respectively. The HEMA unit was found to be more reactive than MMA unit in the copolymer. The overlapped and complex proton and carbon-13 spectra are resolved with the help of DEPT and 2D HSQC spectra. The α -methyl, quaternary, carbonyl and methylene carbon resonance signals were found to be sensitive to configurational sequences but not to compositional sequences. The methyl, quaternary and carbonyl carbons were assigned upto triad configurational sequences while methylene carbon resonance signal was assigned upto tetrad configurational sequences. The various types of couplings between protons of different groups in HEMA/MMA copolymers were assigned completely by TOCSY spectrum. The couplings of carbonyl carbon with methoxy protons and oxy methylene carbon with hydroxyl proton have been assigned with the help of HMBC spectrum.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Department of Science and Technology (DST), Delhi, for providing financial support.

References

- G. D. Barrett, I. J. Constable and A. D. Steward, *J. Cataract. Refract. Surg.*, 1986, **12**, 623.
- H. F. Mark, N. M. Bikalas, C. G. Overberger and G. Menges, *Encycl. Polym. Sci. Eng.*, 1985, **1**, 234.
- L. M. Seifert and R. T. Green, *J. Biomed. Mater. Res.*, 1986, **20**, 919.
- R. Jeyanthi and R. K. Pandurang, *Biomaterials*, 1990, **11**, 238.
- A. Martin, J. Swarbrick and A. Cammarate, "Physical Pharmacy", Philadelphia, PA, Lea and Febiger, 1983, **3**, 579.
- T. Canal and N. A. Peppas, *J. Biomed. Mater. Res.*, 1989, **23**, 1183.
- F. A. Bovey and P. A. Mirau, "NMR of Polymers", Academic Press, New York, 1996.
- R. R. Ernest, G. Bodenhausen and A. Wokaun, "Principles of Nuclear Magnetic Resonance in One and Two Dimensions", Clarendon, Oxford, 1994.
- J. Perlo, V. Demas, F. Casanova, C. A. Meriles, J. Reimer, A. Pines and B. Blumich, *Science*, 2005, **308**, 1279.
- S. Appett, H. Kuhn, F. Hasing and B. Blumich, *Nature*, 2006, **1**.
- D. J. T. Hill, N. G. Moss, P. J. Pomery and A. K. Whittaker, *Polymer*, 2000, **41**, 1287.
- J. V. M. Weaver, I. Bannister, K. L. Robinson, A. X. Bories, S. P. Armes, M. Smallridge and P. McKenna, *Macromolecules*, 2004, **37**, 2395.
- A. S. Brar and Puneeta, *J. Polym. Sci., Part A : Polym. Chem.*, 2006, **44**, 2076.
- A. S. Brar, G. Singh and R. Shankar, *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.*, 2006, **99**, 2174.
- I. Ydens, P. Degee, D. M. Haddleton and P. Dubois, *Eur. Polym. J.*, 2005, **41**, 2255.
- A. S. Brar, G. Singh and R. Shankar, *J. Mol. Str.*, 2004, **703**, 69.
- T. Kelen and F. Tudos, *J. Macro. Sci. Chem.*, 1975, **A9**, 1.
- M. Dube, R. A. Sanyei, A. Penlidis, K. F. Driscoll and P. M. Reilly, *J. Polym. Sci., Part. A : Polym. Chem.*, 1991, **29**, 703.
- A. S. Brar, G. Singh and R. Shankar, *Eur. Polym. J.*, 2004, **40**, 2679.
- J. P. Montheard, M. Chatzopoulos and D. Chapard, *J. M. S. Rev. Macromol. Chem. Phys.*, 1992, **C-32**, 1.
- S. Hooda and A. K. Goyal, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2007, **46**, 899.